

Paper 4

SIBLING RELATIONSHIP AND MENTAL WELL-BEING AMONG YOUNG ADULTS OF INSTITUTIONS FROM BHADRAVATHI IN SHIVAMOGGA DISTRICT

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Abstract

The purpose of this study was to learn about the importance of the relationship between siblings and their mental well-being, including psychotherapeutic intervention. This study adopted purposive sampling method. A sample of 50 young adults belonging to the age ranges 18 to 40 years having biological siblings were selected from 2 institutions in Bhadravathi, Shivamogga district. WEMWBS (Warwick Edinburgh's Mental Well-Being Scale), and ASRQ-S (Adult Sibling Relationship Questionnaire Scale) with the factors Warmth, Conflict, Paternal, and Maternal Rivalry, referred from Wallace's Thesis on "Sibling Relationship", were the scales used to measure The Relationship of Siblings and their Mental Well-Being. This study used SPSS and Descriptive analysis to interpret and describe the data. Therapeutic intervention such as Rational Emotive Behavior Therapy, Post Modern Approaches' Solution Focused Therapy, Narrative Therapy, Virginia Satir's Human Validation process, and Jay Haley and Cloe Madanes' Strategic Family therapy can be used to change Dysfunctional patterns in the family, and enhance Family bonding and thus improve the mental health of the people.

Keywords: Sibling Relationship- Warmth, Conflict, Paternal and Maternal Rivalry, Mental Well-Being, Therapeutic Intervention, Young Adults.

1. INTRODUCTION

Sibling relationship has an impact on Mental Well-Being. Healthy sibling relationships can significantly benefit us later in life. Those with positive sibling relationships report higher life satisfaction and lower rates of depression later in life. Also in times of illness and traumatic events, siblings provide emotional, social support to each other. Research shows that this support is common regardless of whether they live together or far away from each other (Lohmann, 2014). Sibling relationship incorporates actions, verbal and nonverbal communications between individuals who share the same biological parents (Cicirelli, 1991). (Wallace, 2012). According to (Cicirelli, 1994), sibling relationships play an important role not only in the family life but by influencing the way that the family functions within society.

To learn more about sibling relationship, mental wellbeing and therapeutic intervention, an attempt has been made to review the literatures on this topic: Article "Theoretical

Perspectives on Sibling Relationships.” Review To stimulate interest in sibling research and to serve as a guide for future investigations by family scholars, they analyze four theoretical psychologically oriented perspectives—(a) psychoanalytic-evolutionary, (b) social psychological, (c) social learning, and (d) family-ecological systems. Most research on siblings has focused on childhood and adolescence, their review highlights these developmental periods, but they also incorporate the limited research on adult sibling relationships, including in formulating suggestions for future research on this fundamental family relationship. According to Happiness and Human Potentials, Wellbeing is a complex construct that concerns optimal experience and functioning. (Rayan & Deci, 2001) State that current research on well-being has been derived from two general perspectives: The Hedonic Approach: focuses on happiness and defines well-being in terms of pleasure attainment and pain avoidance. The Eudaimonic approach: focuses on meaning and self-realization and defines well-being in terms of the degree to which the person is fully functioning. In the Human Validation Process Model, Satir (1988) outlined four communication stances that people tended to adopt under stress: blaming, placating, super reasonable, and irrelevant. The antidote to these stress communications is congruence, by which Satir ment emotional honesty, in which one speaks for oneself, stays grounded (or centered), and is able to both share what she or he is feeling and ask for what is needed.

2. AIM

The aim of this study was to know the significance of Sibling relationship, and Mental Well-Being among young adults and comprise Psycho-therapeutic intervention. The main objectives of this study was to learn about Sibling Relationship, Mental Well-Being, analyze Sibling Relationship and Mental Well-Being among young adults, and to facilitate the role of a Psychotherapist to enhance the sibling relationship and mental well-being, This study adopted the Descriptive Analysis as research design.

3. FINDINGS

Mental well-being of the respondents was assessed by using Warwick Edinburgh mental well-being scale with 14 positive statements in it. Sibling Relationship was assessed by adding the dimensions of warmth (Intimacy, Emotional Support, and knowledge) and Conflict (quarreling, Antagonism, Dominance), paternal and maternal Rivalry.

Mental well-being of the respondents has been highlighted in three different tables Viz. table 1, table 2 and, table 3.

The first table indicates that, 24 percent of the respondents rarely felt optimistic, 8 percent of them felt optimistic some of the time, 12 percent of them often felt optimistic and 46 percent of the respondents felt optimistic all of the time. 2 percent of the respondents rarely felt useful 72 percent of the respondents felt useful some of the time and 26 percent of the respondents often felt valued. 4 percent of the respondents said that they are never interested in other people 16 percent of the respondents thought that they are interested in other people some of the time 76 percent of the respondents often felt interested in other people and 4 percent of the respondents felt interested in other people all of the time.

MENTAL WELL-BEING OF THE RESPONDENTS

Statements	None of the time	Rarely	Some of the time	Often	All of the time
Feeling optimistic	0	12 24%	4 8%	11 22%	23 46%
Feeling useful	0	1 2%	36 72%	13 26%	0
Feeling interested in other people	2 4%	0	8 16%	38 76%	2 4%

THE RESULT OF EMOTIONAL SUPPORT AMONG SIBLINGS

Statements(Emotional support)	Never	Rarely	Occasionally	Regularly
How much do you try to cheer this sibling up when he/she is feeling down?	4 8%	7 14%	7 14%	32 64%
How much can you count on this sibling to be supportive when you are feeling stressed?	A little	A lot		
	32 64%	18 36%		
When this sibling is stressed are you more likely to provide emotional or practical support?	Emotional support	Practical support	Both	Neither
	11 22%	32 64%	7 14%	0
How often do you discuss important decisions with this sibling	Never	Rarely	Occasionally	Regularly
	6 12%	0	33 66%	11 22%

The table above shows emotional support between siblings 8 percent of the respondents never tried to cheer up their sibling when he/she was feeling down, 14 percent of them rarely tried to cheer their sibling up. Of which, 64 percent of the respondents counted a little on this sibling to be supportive when they were feeling stressed and 36 percent of them were able to count a lot on their sibling to be supportive when they were feeling stressed. 22 percent of the respondents were able to provide emotional support when their siblings have stress, 64 percent were more likely to provide practical support when their sibling was stressed and 14 percent were more likely to offer both emotional and practical support. 12 percent of them never discussed important decisions with their sibling 66 percent of the respondents occasionally discussed important decisions with their sibling and 22 percent of them discussed important decisions with their sibling on a regular basis.

The factors that influence mental well-being and sibling relationship could be societal norms, social pressure, parenting style, and parent-child relationship, family dysfunction, social support system, high/low self-esteem, work, school and college environment, physical and mental abuse.

Solution-focused therapy is well suited for people with adjustment disorders, and for problems of anxiety and depression. According to Family Therapy, the family is viewed from an interactive and systematic perspective. The family provides the context for understanding how individuals function in relation to others and how they behave. Treatment deals with a family unit.

The family therapist functions as a teacher, coach, model, and consultant. The family learns ways to detect and solve problems that are keeping members stuck and it learns about patterns that have been transmitted from generation to generation some approaches focus on the role of therapist as an expert; others concentrate on intensifying what is going on in the here and now of the family session. All family therapists are connected with the process of family interaction and teaching patterns of communication.

4. RECOMMENDATION/ SUGGESTIONS

As this study was done only on young adults, cross-sectional study considering also the middle-aged and the elderly in sibling Relationship study is recommended because the previous studies have found that there is a close bond between siblings as they grow older. It is recommended to focus on gender difference with regards to sibling relationship and mental well-being. Depending on parenting style, how the older sibling form a relationship with the younger one can be taken into consideration for this study. Causes for Maternal Rivalry and Paternal rivalry could be lack of mutual understanding, un-forgiveness among couples that may indirectly affect their children in a negative way, miscommunication, jealousy, manipulating children to get their work done, causing children to quarrel with each other thus destroying family bond. This can be prevented using Virginia Satir's Human Validation Process Model and Jay-Haley and Cloe Madanes' Strategic Family Therapy and through role-modeling as well as making family to learn communication skills and assertiveness training. Studies have found that parental support may create an atmosphere in the family highlighting the importance of helping each other which lasts to adulthood.(Voorpostel and Blieszner; 2008), (Wallace, 2012). Through family therapy (intervention of a Family Therapist), dysfunctions in the family can be evaded and built positive and healthy families. Rational Emotive Behavior therapy by Albert Ellis, Family Systems Therapy, Postmodern Approaches (Solution Focused Brief Therapy; Narrative Therapy), and assertiveness training is found to be helpful in dealing with miscommunication, misunderstanding, and rivalry in the family.

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